

An Approach for Change Management in Agile Software Development Projects

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This project aims to explore and suggest a comprehensive approach to managing changes in software projects. As software development environment grow in complexity and dynamism, it becomes crucial to understand how organizations handles changes across the project lifecycle. This encompasses not only shifts in client requirements but also technological advancement, team dynamics, and other variables.

Planning

Developing an approach capable of supporting change management during the agile development of software projects in small to medium-sized enterprises.

PICOC

- **Population:** Agile method
- **Intervention:** Change management
- **Comparison:**
- **Outcome:** Impact
- **Context:**

Research Questions

1. RQ1: What are the impacts of changes during project development in terms of quality, cost, and schedule?
2. RQ2: Which types of changes have the most impact on project development?
3. RQ3: How are these changes managed and communicated to the team?
4. RQ4: Does the use of agile methodologies help manage, accept, and implement these changes in a way that does not significantly impact the project?

Keywords and Synonyms

Keyword	Synonyms
Agile method	Agile development, Agile method, Agile software development
Change management	Change control
Impact	Impacts

Search String

("Agile method" OR "Agile development" OR "Agile software development") AND ("Change management" OR "Change control") AND ("Impact" OR "Impacts")

Sources

- IEEE Digital Library (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>)
- Snowballing

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Articles discussing the impacts of change on software development, including quality, cost, schedule, and project performance
- Articles evaluating the effectiveness of agile methodologies in change management
- Publications presenting challenges and mitigation strategies related to change management
- Studies addressing the application of agile methodologies in change contexts
- Studies focused on change management in software development projects
- Studies including comparisons of different types of changes (requirements, technologies, teams)

Exclusion Criteria:

- Articles not addressing agile methodologies or discussing only technical aspects unrelated to change management
- Articles not including comparisons or analyses of the impacts of changes
- Articles not written in English
- Non-peer-reviewed technical reports
- Publications about some conference proceeding, journal, or some other collection of papers/publications.
- Publications not discussing challenges or mitigation strategies in change management
- Publications whose full text is not available for download, in their complete form, in the digital libraries, nor through any other way without costs for the researcher
- Studies exclusively focused on large enterprises or industrial contexts not applicable to small and/or medium-sized enterprises
- Studies not focused on change management in software development projects

Quality Assessment Checklist

Questions:

- Does the study directly address change management in agile software development project?
- Are the study participants representative of the context of interest (e.g., agile development, small or medium-enterprises, teams)?

- Are the study's conclusions relevant and do they have practical implications for software project management?
- Does the article address how to handle changes throughout the software development lifecycle (e.g., requirement changes, technological advancements, or team changes)?
- Does the study discuss challenges in change management, such as resistance to change, communication gaps, or implementation obstacles?
- Does the article evaluate how changes impact project performance, including quality, adherence to schedule, and/or cost?

Answers:

- Yes
- Partially
- No

Data Extraction Form

- Study Title
- Authors
- Year of Publication
- Source of Publication
- Type of Study
- What are the main objectives of the study?
- Does the study address change management in agile software development projects?
- What type of changes are discussed in the study?
- Does the study discuss challenges in change management?
- What specific challenges are mentioned?
- Does the study assess how changes impact project performance?
- What aspects of project performance are evaluated?
- Does the study provide practical recommendations for change management in agile projects?

Conducting

Digital Libraries Search Strings

Imported Studies

- **IEEE Digital Library:** 23
- **Scopus:** 147
- **Snowballing:** 0